

Lingbao dafa

also known as “靈寶大法”, “Duren dafa 度人大法”

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Religious Practice, Daoism, Chinese Religion, Religious Group, Lingbao Daoism

Lingbao dafa 靈寶大法, the Great Rites of Numinous Treasure, also known as Duren dafa 度人大法, the Great Rites of Salvation, is an aggregate of Daoist ritual practices. In the Daoist Canon, certain scriptures, such as the Great Rites of Shangqing Lingbao (Shangqing Lingbao dafa 上清靈寶大法), classified into the Lingbao Daoist tradition have comprehensive descriptions and instructions for the practice. By using series of techniques like methods (fa 法), incantations (zhou 呪/咒), talisman (fu 符), and statements (shu 疏), it first applied to self-promotion to accommodate the body and mind with the Dao; and then, it was put to use in public ritual performance for universal salvation and expel demonic forces. The Lingbao dafa is a production of a combination of many new exorcisms and therapeutic methods in the Song-Yuan time (12th-14th century). Continuing the mediation practices in Shangqing 上清 [Supreme Purity] revelation, the Lingbao dafa used meditation techniques like visualization, concentration, and inner observation for the inner body promotion. The Shenxiao 神霄 [Divine Empyrean] tradition was borrowed by the Lingbao dafa in terms of its exorcism through the Thunder Rites (leifa 雷法). Attached to the view of deliverance in the Scripture on Salvation (Duren jing 度人經), it built on the traditional Daoist Retreat ritual (zhaiyi 齋儀) to formulate many salvation approaches, mainly practiced in the Yellow Register Retreat (Huanglu zhai 黃籙齋). In the Lingbao dafa, the most distinctive ritual performed in the Yellow Register Retreat is the Liturgy of Salvation of the Deceased through the Alchemical Refinement (liandu 鍊度儀). Because the Lingbao dafa featured in absorbing and transforming rituals from different branches of Daoism, Buddhism, and popular religions, it is hard for scholars to identify the exact relationship between the Lingbao dafa and other Song-Yuan new methods. Although the movement of Lingbao Daoism appeared as early as the 4th century CE, the organized practice of Lingbao dafa was not formed until the 12th century. It was popularized in Southern Song China in the lower Yangzi River Basin, however, its spreading was not limited to Zhejiang 浙江, Jiangxi 江西, and Jiangsu 江蘇, but also as south as Guangdong 廣東. The Lingbao dafa, unlike many conservative religious ritual performances, was a very popular practice among both religious specialists and non-religious. All people without caring for their social, political, and economic background could be a practitioner of the Lingbao dafa, even when they still kept their other beliefs with them in Buddhism, Confucianism, local beliefs, etc. Ritual masters well known for their practice or compilation in the Lingbao dafa trace back to the Ning Quanzhen 寧全真 (1101-81, also known as Ning Benli 寧本立), 王契真 (fl. ca. 1250), 金允中 (fl. 1224-1225), 林靈真 (1239-1303, also known as Lin Weifu 林偉夫) and so forth. Moreover, the Daoist master Lu Xiujing 陸修靜 (406-477), due to his contribution in the composition of liturgical texts and normalization of early Daoist Retreat, his work on the early Lingbao tradition is a fundamental source when examining the Lingbao dafa. All in all, the Lingbao dafa was a medley of many new Song-Yuan Daoist methods; it witnessed the rapid growth of Daoism in the aspect of self-cultivation practice and public ritual service, thus, a valuable material concerning the Daoist ritual history.

Date Range: 400 CE - 1400 CE

Region: Jiangnan Area

Region tags: China, Yangzi River Valley

The main masters of the Lingbao dafa were either natives or activating in the most part of Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, and Anhui province, the normally classified Jiangnan Area.

参与者的状态

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

来源

理解这一问题的书面资料：

—来源 1: Bokenkamp, Stephen R. "Sources of the Ling-pao Scriptures." *Tantric and Taosit studies in honour of R. A. Stein*, no.2 (1983): 434-485.

—来源 2: Boltz, Judith M. *A Survey of Taoist Literature: Tenth to Seventeenth Centuries*. Berkeley: University of California, 1987.

—来源 3: Chang, Chaojan 張超然. "Zhaiké yú jīngfǎ: Sòng-Yuán Huánglǔ zhāifǎ yánjiū" (齋科與經法：宋元黃籙齋法研究). *Daoism: Religion, History & Society 道教研究學報：宗教、歷史與社會*, no. 11 (2019): 63-105.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

—来源1 URL: <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5a0001/>

—来源1 描述: Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Lingbao wuliang duren shangpin miaojing" (Wonderous Scripture of the Upper Chapters of the Numinous Treasure on Limitless Salvation)

—来源2 URL: <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5g0030/>

—来源2 描述: Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Shangqing Lingbao dafa" (Great Method of the Numinous Treasure of Highest Clarity) by Wang Qizhen

—来源3 URL: <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5g0032/>

—来源3 描述: Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Shangqing Lingbao dafa" (Great Method of the Numinous Treasure of Highest Clarity) by Jin Yunzhong

Notes: More Lingbao scriptures on the topic of Lingbao dafa: <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5a0220/>. Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Lingbao wuliang duren shangjing dafa" (Great Rites of the Superior Scripture of the Numinous Treasure on Limitless Salvation) <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5b0250/>. Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Lingbao yujian" (Jade Mirror of the Numinous Treasure) <http://kanripo.org/text/KR5b0150/>. Primary source of the Taoist Canon "Lingbao lingjiao jidu jinshu" (Golden Book of Salvation according to the Lingbao Tradition)

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

一是

Notes: The Lingbao Daoism was commonly agreed by many scholars that borrowed religious elements from other religions. The Lingbao dafa scriptures reflected an influence of Buddhist language, and developed a system of pseudo-Sanskrit terms used for incantation. Those pseudo-Sanskrit terms use Chinese characters to mimic the vocalization of Sanskrit found in Buddhist and Hindu recitations, but have no actual meaning in Buddhism. The terms usually appear before a group of deities' titles, like an announcement of summoning the gods. The well-organized ritual of universal salvation was on the one hand, inspired by the Duren jing, on the other hand, it was driven under the pressure of competition with Buddhist ritual in funeral market. Presently, it is still popular in many regions like Taiwan, Guangdong, and Hongkong to invite Daoist ritual masters perform a salvation ritual in funeral. Because of the ethics of filial piety in Confucianism, the Daoist salvation ritual gradually turned from saving the Daoist disciplines only to provide public service for other civics. Therefore, Daoist ritual can fulfil the need of ancestor worship by request of people with different social background.

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

一是

Notes: The main argument lies in the conflict between the sect of Eastern Florescence (Donghua 東華), also called Tiantai Lingbao 天台靈寶 (because of its origination in the Mount Tiantai 天台山 in Zhejiang 浙江 province) and another Lingbao sect represented by the master Jin Yunzhong 金允中 (fl.1224-1225) derived from the Zhengyi 正一 group in the Mount Longhu 龍虎山 in Jiangxi 江西 province. The masters who were most representative in the Donghua sect were: Ning Benli 寧本立 (1101-1181), Lin Lingzhen 林靈真 (also known as Lin Weifu 林偉夫, 1239-1303), and Wang Qizhen 王契真 (fl. ca. 1250). They were more radical in renewing traditional Lingbao teachings with new exorcistic Tianxin tradition. While Jin Yunzhong who was more conservative and wished to restore the ancient tradition from the Zhengyi or Tianshi tradition, so the Lingbao dafa could become more authentic and dignified. The result of these differences was that, the sect represented by the master Jin Yunzhong kept a stricter and closer relationship with the authority in the Mount Longhu, yet the Tiantai Lingbao was largely spread among lay people, including merchants, both court and local officials, elites, and all people disregarding their financial and social status.

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

一是

Notes: The Lingbao dafa was an achievement of intermixture of many existent practices. Following early Daoist traditions such as the Celestial Masters Daoism (Tianshi dao 天師道), it included the section of "sending petitions (to deities)" in its own rites. It also used self-cultivation methods from the Shangqing 上清 Revelation like visualization and meditation. Meanwhile, the Lingbao dafa included other practices from the new Daoist exorcistic and therapeutic traditions in Song-Yuan time. For example, it accepted the way of communicating with gods during ordination rituals which was borrowed from the Rectifying Rites of Celestial Heart (Tianxin zhengfa 天心正法); and the Thunder rites (leifa 雷法) of the Shenxiao 神霄 sect for exorcism. One of the most creative and important ritual in the Lingbao dafa, the Salvation

through Refinement (liandu 鍊度), was a combination of these practices and the practice of Inner Alchemy (neidan 内丹) that flourished since the late-Tang dynasty.

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

— 是

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

— 是

↳ 与生俱来（成员身份在这种社会是默认的）：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 基于个人选择：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由社会阶层赋予：

— 否

Notes: It was encouraged to learn the Lingbao dafa for people from diverse backgrounds including officials in court, local officials, literati, merchants, workmen, peasants and so on. These practitioners (who were not ordained as a formal Daoist) just learn the technique for self-promotion in the physical or/and mental perspective. Since they skipped the certification as a Daoist priest, they can neither host a small-scale nor a large-scale ritual.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由特定年龄阶段赋予：

— 否

Notes: The discipline shows that people who wish to devote to Daoism can receive register (lu

籙) starting from their seventh birthday (for female, it starts from ten year-old). When they getting older, they can have higher rank. However, there has no absolute rules concerning about the age. For reference, see primary sources in the Daoist Canon: DZ 1236 Taishang chujia chuandu yi 太上出家傳度儀 [Ordination Ceremony for Those Who Leave the Family] DZ 1237 Sandong xiudao yi 三洞修道儀 [Protocol for the Practice of the Tao of the Three Caverns] Please note that, we are only able to draw conclusion based on the situation of monastic Daoists, gongguan daoshi 宮觀道士, Daoists who live and lean on a monastery. Those huojia daoshi 火居道士, Daoists who live at home and married, might not follow the exact strict rules. Therefore, to tell their religious lives will depend on analysis of case by case.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由性别赋予：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由参与特定仪式赋予：

— 是

Notes: To leave the family and take an oath to become a Daoist is a very serious and long process. The prerequisite of studying the Lingbao dafa is to become a Lingbao Daoist certified by the Initiation and Ordination ritual (shoudu yi 授度儀). The Ordination ritual in the Lingbao tradition was divided into three stages. Based on the criteria of certain precepts (jie 戒), registers (lu 籙), methods (fa 法) and scriptures (jing 經), junior Daoist disciples first become so called Pupil of Initial Covenant (chumeng dizi 初盟弟子); then promote to the position of Ritual Master of Cavernous Mystery (dongxuan fashi 洞玄法師) by achieving the level of Middle Covenant (zhongmeng 中盟); finally the Supreme Ritual Master of Cavernous Mystery (wushang dongxuan fashi 無上洞玄法師) after they complete all the requirements of Great Covenant (dameng 大盟) which is very difficult. After the Daoists are ready to receive the Middle Covenant, they can start ask for instruction of the Lingbao dafa from their mentors through the Transmission ritual (chuandu yi 傳度儀). The Lingbao tradition believed that their scriptures are Heavenly Writs (tianwen 天文), a teachings transmitted directly from the deities in heaven, therefore, the mentors in the study of the Lingbao dafa are no more than agents helping communicating the disciple with the heavenly gods. The series of rituals above are expected to conduct only in sacred places for the Lingbao Daoism, the Mountain Longhu and the Mountain Gezao, both in Jiangxi. However, the reality is, the rules settled by early priests were not always followed by all Lingbao sects. The Tiantai Lingbao, an innovation sect, did not require their disciples make pilgrimages to the sacred mountain, what's more, the transmission of the Lingbao dafa was open to all public than Lingbao Daoists who possess the basic Daoist status. For reference: DZ 528 Lingbao shoudu yi 靈寶授度儀 [Ordination Ritual of the Numinous Treasure] DZ 1241 Chuanshou sanding jingjie falu lüeshuo 傳授三洞經戒法籙略說 [Brief Exposition on the Transmission of the Scriptures, Percepts, Methods and Registers of the Three Caverns]

Reference: 超然 張. 援法入道：南宋靈寶傳度科儀研究. (世維 謝, 世維 謝, Ed.), 經典道教與地方宗教. 臺北: 政大出版社.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由其它因素而赋予：

—是: The revelation from divinity is the most direct way to convert someone into a Daoist.

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

—否

Notes: Generally speaking, the Lingbao tradition was not active in propagating its teachings. On the one hand, it is one of the features of Daoism that it should be very cautious about who have access to the sacred knowledge and in what way. On the other hand, it was up to different branches of Lingbao tradition to choose their way of finding devotees. As a conservative, master Jin Yunzhong (fl.1224-1225) made it very clear that people who casually reveal the method (fa 法), would bear punishment and embroil their nine generations of ancestor in the penalty as well. See DZ 1223 Shangqing Lingbao dafa 上清靈寶大法 [The Great Rites of Shangqing Lingbao], 42: 2b-3a.

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

—是

Notes: It seems unlikely that the Lingbao ritual masters have financial support from the government directly for establishing a temple. However, the ritual performances could be seen as a service that the government would purchase thus increase their income.

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：

—是

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：

—是

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：

—否

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：

—否

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：

—是

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：

—否

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税) :

— 是

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口, 数字)

— 未知领域

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量 (在样本区域人口中的百分比, 数字)

— 未知领域

宗教团体性质【请选其一】 :

— 小型宗教团体 (被视作相关的更大的宗教团体的一部分)

在该宗教团体中是否存在被认可的领导者 :

— 是

Notes: The “leaders” of the Lingbao Daoism, though they have titles and ranks according to Daoist ordination system, they do not share the same power and influence in public or political as the Pope in Western Catholicism. Essentials of a certain rank in Daoist community judged by the possession of register (lu 籙). Higher register means the level of self-cultivation, techniques, ritual performance, and heavenly soldiers under his/her command. A leader, except being able to attain the register, also has reputation in many ways that build him a role model for other Daoist followers, for example, accomplishments in scripture compiling, entitled by royalty, and participation in official ritual.

↳ 这些领导者中有等级制度存在吗 :

— 是

Notes: The different types of registers (lu 籙) that a priest attains, represent the level and rank the priest currently stays in the Daoist ordination system. Receiving a register, means that those deities who adhesive to that type of register would be at the adherent's disposal, i.e. the practitioners during ritual performance have ability to require the transcendence power from those deities. Higher level of register not only grants the priest higher status in the Daoist community, but also comes with higher position in the Daoist pantheon after they achieve enlightenment.

↳ 多个宗教社区各有其领导者, 领导者之间没有层级 :

— 否

↳ ‘地区’领导者，监督一个或者多个地方领导者（比如，主教）：

— 否

↳ 宗教团体中只有一个领导者，掌管着该采样地区内所有其它领导者：

— 我不知道

↳ 宗教团体中存在一个委员会或者领导小组，掌管同该采样区域内所有其他的领导者：

— 我不知道

↳ 请估算该宗教领袖等级制度中存在多少级的层级：

— 我不知道

↳ 领袖们被认为有超自然能力或者特质吗：

— 是

Notes: Possession of a Daoist register means that the priest has right and ability to command heavenly officials and soldiers listed in the register (in the register there is a list of deities' names who the holder could command). Supernatural power thus has two aspects: 1) the priest him-/her- self's supernatural power, such as communicating with deities, foreseeing the future, etc.; 2) the supernatural power that he/her has access to borrow and use for own convenience.

↳ 能力通过前世的修为获得：

— 否

↳ 能力通过今生的修为获得：

— 是

↳ 能力由继承而来：

— 否

↳ 能力从超自然的生灵传递而来：

— 是

↳ 能力从另一个人处通过文化传递得来（比如，老师）

— 是

↳ 能力从他们所担任的领袖职位得到：

—是

经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

—是

Reference: 文龍 陳. 王契真《上清靈寶大法》研究. 濟南: 齊魯書社.

Reference: Chi-tim Lai. The Daoist Identity of the Yellow Register Retreat in the Southern Song: A Case Study of Jin Yunzhong's Great Rites of Lingbao. *Cahiers d'Extrême-Asie.*, 20

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

—是

Notes: The written scriptures collected in the Daoist Canon (Daozang 道藏) that directly deal with the practice of Lingbao dafa are abundant. Starting from the very beginning, the first text worth mentioning is the Wonderful Scripture of the Upper Chapters of the Numinous Treasure on Limitless Salvation (Lingbao wuliang duren shangpin miaojing 靈寶無量度人上品妙經), briefly, Scripture on Salvation (Duren jing 度人經) dated back to the fifth century. This text does not have the rite or method (fa 法) popularized in the Southeastern China as we see later on since the Song dynasty, but all the ideology of salvation that the Lingbao dafa bore came from the instruction of this Duren jing. Almost all the later texts on the Lingbao dafa see the Duren jing as their primary classic. The second and third scripture are both titled the Great Rites of Shangqing Lingbao (Shangqing Lingbao dafa 上清靈寶大法) that came into being around the Southern Song period. However, the issues like what is the formulation of Lingbao dafa and how should it be performed are disagreed in these two scriptures. One of the Shangqing Lingbao dafa was compiled by the master Wang Qizhen 王契真 (fl.ca.1250) according to the teaching of his master Ning Benli 寧本立 (1101-1181, identified as earlier codifier of the practice). This sect of Lingbao tradition was comparatively innovation than another. It claims that their doctrines descend from heaven by the perfected (zhenren 真人), and their principles were more flexible than any human beings can be ordained and practice the Lingbao dafa. The other Shangqing Lingbao dafa edited by master Jin Yunzhong 金允中 (fl.1224-1225) was an attempt to chase the history of Lingbao dafa back to ancient masters. Therefore, it took the authenticity very seriously and not all people were qualified to practice and perform the Lingbao dafa. The forth scripture is the Golden Book of Salvation according to the Lingbao tradition (Lingbao lingjiao jidu jinshu 靈寶領教濟度金書). This work builds on the two Shangqing Lingbao dafa, as the name indicated, aiming at salvation and therapeutic rituals for society during Yuan time (1271-1368). Its editor was a native Wenzhou master, Lin Lingzhen 林靈真. Last but not least, the Great Rites of the Superior Scripture of the Numinous Treasure on Limitless Salvation (Lingbao wuliang duren shangjing dafa 靈寶無量度人上經大法) was an example of Lingbao dafa merged with Shenxiao tradition. Under the influence of new practice, sublimation in the inner body weighed heavier. There are apparently more scriptures and

liturgical texts on Lingbao dafa inside and out the Daoist Canon. It is important to keep in mind that all these new Lingbao dafa text established on early Daoist traditions and cannot be examined independently.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 它们是口述的吗 :

一是

Notes: The Lingbao dafa was considered the oral instructions of the Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 经典的来源和一个 (或一组) 故事有关吗 :

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示 :

一是

Notes: The Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊)

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示 :

一是

Notes: The Lingbao dafa was an oral instruction told by the Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊). When the oral teaching revealed, it was not accessible to the human kind. The Supreme Empire of the Five Elders (Wulao shangdi 五老上帝), the Perfected with Wonderous Behaviors (Miaoxing zhenren 妙行真人), the Divine Kings of the Ten Directions (Shifang shenwang 十方神王), and many other deities initiated the Lingbao dafa to the civil world, that is how the Lingbao dafa started to popularize.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由至高无上的神启示 :

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来源于凡人：

— 我不知道

↳ 这一经典是否可以改变：

— 否

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：

— 否

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：

— 否

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：

— 是

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

— 是

Notes: The Palace for the Veneration of the Perfected (Chongzhen gong 崇真宮) in the Mount Gezao (Gezao shan 閤皂山) in Jiangxi was the most important temple for Lingbao Daoism.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在一般的定居地，所有宗教纪念性质建筑、纪念物面积所占百分比是多少：

— 未知领域

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的面积，以平方米计
— 我不知道

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的高度，以米计
— 我不知道

↳ 一般纪念物、建筑的尺寸，平方米
— 我不知道

↳ 一般纪念建筑、纪念物的高度，米
— 我不知道

↳ 在最大的定居地，所有宗教纪念物、纪念建筑总体面积所占区域百分比是多少？
— 未知领域

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

— 是

↳ 陵墓
— 是

↳ 公墓
— 是

↳ 庙宇
— 是

↳ 圣坛
— 是

↳ 用于礼拜的标志性建筑
— 是

↳ 大规模集会点（庭院、广场等，用可见物或结构永久划分出来的场所）

— 是

↳ 其它种类的宗教纪念性建筑物

— 我不知道

是否存在表征标志

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

— 在人

— 在家里

— 只在宗教公共场所

— 在一些公共场所

Notes: Icons of deities appear in various places in daily prayer and during ritual performance. People who have faith on the Lingbao Daoism may hang paintings and set up shrines for the Three Purities: Jade Purity (Yuqing 玉清), Supreme Purity (Shangqing 上清), and Great Purity (Taiqing 太清), along with other deities in the belief. In religious places, such as temples, monasteries, or home of a Daoist priest, except displaying icons in each hall for worshipping, there are icons present on the altar when conducting a ritual. Which deities' icons to be displayed on the altar depends solely on the type and the aim of the ritual. If it is a ritual of salvation for the deceased, then the Celestial Worthy Who Relieves Suffering (Jiuku tianzun 救苦天尊) and other related deities would show up in ritual place (daochang 道場). Besides, in either religious or ordinary festivals, some icons may be displayed on public realms like plazas for certain goals. For further reading, see Chang Chao-jan 張超然. "Tang Song daojiao zhaiyi zhong de 'lishi cunnian' ji qi yuanliu kaolun" 唐宋道教齋儀中的「禮師存念」及其源流考論. *Qinghua xuebao* 清華學報, no. 3 (2015), 381-413.

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 眼睛 (是否写实)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然的存在(兽形)

—是

↳ 超自然的存在(地貌外形)

—是

Notes: In the Lingbao Daoism, as well as described by the Lingbao dafa, there is the belief in the Five Directions (wufang 五方). Several objects correspond with this belief. First, in heaven, the Five Empires (wudi 五帝) as supernatural beings reside in the Five Sacred Peaks (wuyue 五岳). Then, on earth, their true forms (zhenxing 真形) are inscribed in talismans and paintings to guide people when they entering the sacred mounts. Otherwise, people who enter in remote mountains without knowledge of the true form of this mountain will be hurt or get lost in there.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然的存在(人形)

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然的存在(抽象的象征符号)

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 对来世的描绘

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 教义方面 (比如, 十字架、三位一体、密特拉教符号)

—我不知道

↳ 人类

—是

↳ 表征有其它特色 :

—我不知道

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

一是

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：

“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

一是

有朝圣活动吗：

一是

Notes: The Mount of the Dragon and Tiger, Longhu shan 龍虎山, is the authoritative place for Daoism. Masters who gained their register from elsewhere, would still want to visit the Mount Longhu for an acknowledgement from the orthodox Daoism.

↳ 朝圣活动如何严格：

— 可选择的（常见）

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

一是

Notes: Ancient Chinese ideas regarding death and after life are perfectly reflected and developed in Daoism. In the scriptures of Lingbao dafa, the body and souls are depicted in detail. There are three hun-souls (魂, or cloud-souls) and seven po-souls (魄, or white-souls) in human body. When people are alive, these souls get along well and keep a balance. After the death, the three hun-souls which are light and represent the yang will go up, while the seven heavy po souls, which represent the yin go down. The po-souls buried with the body and descend to subterranean realm, they will stay there until they ultimately vanish. The integration of the three hun-soul, during the salvation ritual of the deceased of Lingbao dafa, is the target that the ritual masters try to save from the purgatory underground and help them to rebirth, moreover, even ascend up to heaven. In short, the basic ideas of Chinese thought on the afterlife and souls, on the one hand, have a chance to bloom in the Lingbao dafa, on the other, the Lingbao dafa flourished some new ideas and ways of salvation.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 精神 - 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质

一是

Notes: The souls are weight much less than human body, so they can fly fast and pass through walls.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

对来世的信仰：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

— 是

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

— 是

Notes: Afterlife, at least from the perspective of the Lingbao dafa, includes two steps and therefore two realms. First, the souls of the deceased stay in a transfer station after they leave the body, which is a status similar to antarābhava (the intermediate state; or zhongyin 中陰) in Buddhism. The transfer station is analogous to a court in this world. A record of each person's behavior, merit, morality will be counted then decide where this person's souls will go next. A common place in the belief of Lingbao dafa, though might be slightly different depending on each branches of Daoism, is the Great Ministry of Lay of the Numinous Treasure (Lingbao dafa si 靈寶大法司). The souls after their trial will go through different types of purgatories to expiate their sins. The next step is through ritual performance rescuing the souls from purgatory and helping them reborn in the next life or ascend to Heaven relying on the merit they accumulated before death. A salvation ritual thus is a fast way to shorten the period of the souls' redemption in the purgatory, at the same time, express the descendants' filial piety towards their ancestor.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

— 否

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

— 是

Notes: It is usually believed that afterlife is spatially below the earth.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

— 否

在这个世界上的转世

— 否

Notes: There has no concept of reincarnation in Daoism. However, there are believes of where human

being will go after pass the boundary of death. In Lingbao dafa, the central function is to save the souls of the deceased from the purgatory (yu 獄). These souls stay in this transitional bureaucracy waiting for the trial to decide where they will end up and what they will become. Through this salvation ritual in Lingbao dafa, these souls have chance to ascend to heaven and become a transcendent, or rebirth in next life as human. Merit, yet, is the standard in judging and deciding their destination. Even the livings spend a lot to conduct a ritual for their deceased relatives, their previous merit is the most crucial part.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: It was not mentioned in the scriptures related to the Lingbao dafa, but there was a relative ritual practice of putting Grave-Securing Stone and Grave-Securing Writs in the coffin around the body for protection. Among the Six Dynasties period (222-589), archaeological evidences show that people already practiced the ritual later on became an organized Daoist ritual in Tang dynasty (618-907) known as the Retreat of Refinement of the Five (spirits) for Revivifying the Corpse (wulian shengshi zhai 五鍊生尸齋). The belief is that, the five directions (east, west, south, north, and center) and the Five Transcendents of Salvation through Refinement (Liandu wuxian 鍊度五仙) provide power of dispelling any disturbance from the spirits underground and refining the corpse. The stones and writs with identical inscribe are the token for summoning those transcendents. This belief to a certain degree generated the core idea of Salvation through Refinement (liandu 鍊度) in the Lingbao dafa, and the practice of wulian shengshi was still alive in Song (960-1279) funeral rituals. See DZ 369 Taishang Dongxuan Lingbao miedu wulian shengshi miaojing 太上洞玄靈寶滅度五鍊生尸妙經 [The Marvelous Scripture of Salvation through Extinction: Refinement of the Five (spirits) for Revivifying the Corpse]

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

是否存在陪葬品：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

个人物品：

— 我不知道

有价值的物品：

— 我不知道

↳ 其他陪葬品：

— 是

Notes: In the belief of Five Direction, the Grave-Securing Stone (zhenmu shi 鎮墓石) and Grave-Securing Writs (zhenmu wen 鎮墓文) are largely used in believers' tombs. Many archaeological excavations shown up these years. However, it is still not very clear in what situation the living relatives choose to bury the Stone or/and the Writs in the tomb.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

有正式的葬礼吗：

— 是

Notes: Generally speaking, people in ancient China adopted Confucianist funeral rites and bury the body in the ground. Nonetheless, the pervasive belief of Liberation Corpse (shijie 尸解) (also glossed as "corpse release") among different forms of Daoism is that the soul(s) releases from the mortal coil to transcend into a state of immortality. Therefore, if this belief changes the custom of Lingbao Daoists burial is unknown.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 树立纪念碑：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 葬于公墓：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 葬于家庭墓地或教堂地下室

— 我不知道

↳ 在家里 (埋在房屋地下或者在有正常家庭活动的地方)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

- ↳ 其他正式的葬礼形式：
— 我不知道

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

- ↳ 有一个至上之神存在

— 是

Notes: The Celestial Worthy of Original Commencement (Yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊) is recognized in Lingbao dafa as the most highest god in pantheon. The Celestial Worthy passes through all the five kalpa-cycles (jie 劫: Longhan 龍漢, Yankang 延康, Chiming 赤明, Shanghuang 上皇, and Kaihuang 開皇) monitoring the world and interfere with the human world only at the time that human behaviors were most decayed.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

- ↳ 至上之神是人形：

— 是

Notes: Originally, it was believed that Daoist transcendents (xian 仙), deities (shen 神) generating from Qi 炁/氣, a cosmic substance that is formless, therefore cannot be depicted by any human kind. However, under the pressure of religious competition, Daoists have to create the image of divinities for worshipping as a missionary means.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

- ↳ 至上之神是天神

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

- ↳ 至上之神是地府的神灵（地底世界的）：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神与君主不分 (王=至高的神)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 君主被视作至上之神的表现和化身 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神和精英阶层有亲属关系

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神和精英有其它类型的效忠关系

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至高之神是不可质疑的善

— 否

Notes: The disasters, not excluded to famine, flood, earthquake, etc., were sometimes believed the punishment for collective sin of humankind. The supreme high god therefore was the ruler who commanded such catastrophe to purify and renew the profane world. A god who descended tragedy, though he was also the one who grant benevolent, was not always considered unquestionably good.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神的其他特征 :

— 我不知道

↳ 至上之神具有关于这个世界的知识 :

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，至上之神都可以看到你

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— 我不知道

↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇/你将来会做什么 (预测的能力) :

— 我不知道

↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识 :

— 我不知道

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的 (一个或多个) 特定区域 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制 :

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制 :

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 不论你 (在公共场所) 置身何处, 至上之神都可以看到你

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇/你将来会做什么（预测的能力）：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识：

—我不知道

↳ 至上之神对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神能奖赏

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神能惩罚：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神对这个世界上可以施发间接的因果效力：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神展现其积极的情感：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神展现其负面的情感：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神有饥饿感：

— 我不知道

↳ 除了至高之神以外，允许崇拜其他超自然存在吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神具备/展现出其他一些特征：

— 我不知道

↳ 至上之神和生灵有沟通：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在睡梦中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 通过占卜行为：

— 是

Notes: There are many ways to communicate with supernatural beings, specially deities like the Perfected (zhenren 真人), the Perfected Lord (zhenjun 真君), and Generals (jiangjun 將軍) etc. First through visualization, the ritual masters visualize the image of deities in front of him in real human size and form. There are plenty of description in the scriptures of their names, appearances, clothes, holding or wearing objects, their companionate animals and so on, to help the masters picturing them vividly. Secondly, the deities can be summoned by force in the use of talismans (fu 符). Numerous talismans were given in liturgical texts, each fit in a category to serve different functions. What's more, incense is the key to communicate with heavenly gods in almost all the ritual performance not limited in the Lingbao dafa. The section called offering incense (jinxiang 進香) is for this purpose.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

— 我不知道

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

— 是

Notes: In the Lingbao dafa, the souls-body distinction stands in a central position, especially in the salvation ritual for the deceased. It is based on the idea that the hun- and po-souls will leave human body after death. When the po-souls descend to the underground with the buried body, the hun-souls, who are supposed to ascend up to heaven, are also trapped in the underworld. Hence, a Daoist ritual is needed for saving those hun-souls from the purgatory beneath earth.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到

— 是

Notes: During the ritual performance, the souls are led by heavenly officials to actually appear on the ritual altar. Ideally, the souls can be seen, felt and even communicate with the living relatives.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂可以用身体感触到：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 过去人的灵魂对这个世界有所认知：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂至上对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂可以奖赏：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂可以惩罚：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 人类灵魂对这个世界有间接因果效应：

—是

↳ 人类灵魂对人生有记忆：

—是

Notes: As long as the spirits have not yet been reborn, they are ancestors of some family and hence possess all the memory of their previous life.

↳ 人类灵魂展现出积极的情感：

—是

Notes: The belief of receiving blessing from ancestors shows a relationship between the living and their deceased family members. Once the ancestors are happy with their circumstances, that is to say, they reside in a comfortable tomb, have sufficient food and paper money, accept regular worship from their descendants and so on, they provide protection and blessing to their descendants.

↳ 人类灵魂展现出负面的情感：

—是

Notes: Following the previous question, whenever the ancestors inhabit in a dissatisfied, uncomfortable place, or they are lack of necessity, they express negative emotion by disturbing the livings, causing misfortune to their descendants, sending message in dreams, etc.

↳ 人类灵魂有饥饿感：

—是

Notes: In both Chinese thoughts and Daoist beliefs, the souls, or spirits live in the other world the same way as in this one, which make them require supplies like food, clothes, property, etc. after the death. The food for the living, however, cannot be delivered and eaten by the spirits directly. In a section of ritual, transforming the food (zhoushi 呪食), it aims to magically transfer the food, like rice, steamed bun, dumplings, etc. into something that are able for the spirits to enjoy.

↳ 人类灵魂和生灵沟通：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

— 是

Notes: The livings have ability to communicate with the deceased's souls in the daytime and staying awake. Some people who have different body constitutions might be easier to communicate with souls than others.

↳ 在睡梦中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

— 是

Notes: The livings have possibility to be possessed by the deceased's souls. Especially in Taiwan, there are female specialists, known as hongyi 紅姨, provide such services.

↳ 通过占卜行为：

— 是

↳ 只通过专业的宗教人士：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

— 我不知道

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：

— 是

- ↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到：
 - 是

- ↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于特定的领域人类事务：
 - 否

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：
 - 否

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区内无所不知：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区以外无所不知：
 - 是

- ↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，非人类的超自然存都可以看到你：
 - 是

- ↳ 不论你置身何处非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你将来的人生际遇／你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：
 - 是

- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有其他的认知：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：
 - 我不知道
- ↳ 有半人半神的存在：
 - 是
 - Notes: The Perfected (zhenren 真人) in Daoism can somehow be seen as a kind of mixed human-divine beings. Acquiring longevity, immortality, and transcendence are the destiny for people who pursue the Dao all the time in the Daoist history. Some Daoists, when they reach the point of enlightenment and obtain a longer life, some supernatural powers as well, they become so called Zhenren, the Perfected, and thus considered some mixed human-divine beings. Although, sometimes the title of Zhenren might just be a symbol of status, or a granted surname by officials.
- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以被看到：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以用肢体感触到：
 - 是
- ↳ 半人半神的存在对这个世界有所认知：

— 是

↳ 半人半神的存在对于这个世界有意造成因果效应：
— 未知领域

↳ 这些半人半神的存在对这个世界上有间接因果效应：
— 是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出积极的情感：
— 未知领域

↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出负面的情感：
— 未知领域

↳ 这些半人半神的存在有饥饿感：
— 我不知道

↳ 这些半人半神的存在有/展现出一些其他特征：
— 我不知道

↳ 这些半人半神的存在和生灵沟通
— 是

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：
— 是

↳ 在睡梦中：
— 是

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：
— 否

↳ 通过占卜行为：
— 是

↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：

— 是

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：

— 是

Notes: Generally speaking, the supernatural beings are categorized as the Heaven Office (tianguan 天官), the Earth Office (diguan 地官) and the Water Office (shuiguan 水官), normally known as the Three Offices (sanguan 三官). The Heaven Office grants blessing, the Earth Office releases crimes, and the Water Office expels misfortunes. In Daoist ritual, the specialist writes petitions (zhang 章) on behalf of the people in need, and put three copies of that petitions separately on a mountain, bury under the soil, and throw into water symbolizing submit files to these Three Offices. The Heaven Office in a sense overrules the other two Offices.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 万神庙的其他组织方式：

— 我不知道

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

一是

Notes: There are two spheres of supernatural beings that are watching the mankind. One is the interior body gods, and another exterior. According to the Corresponding theory, there is a microcosm inside human body which is an emulation of the macrocosm exists on the planet. Therefore, the deities outside are also have their pairs inside the body. The body gods record our behaviors, minds, and emotions, and report to administrations of concern regularly. Such record, eventually, becomes the criteria to decide where a person will end up in the next life. The exterior gods at the mean time watch the human beings as well, that is why people should always notice their manner and show respect to divinity both in public and at home. Common norms like no-killing, no-lying are included in things that the supernatural beings monitor. Some other standards are more specific for Daoist priests, such as practice the physical body and concentrate the mind. Each action and intention in this life are all count and therefore have consequence to take on the court after death.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 有针对遵守亲社会规范的超自然监视：

亲社会规范是指增加族群中成员协作的规范，包括明显的“道德”或“伦理”规范，也延伸至关于履行合约与誓言，提供热情款待，在紧急情况下互相帮助等等。

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 超自然存在在意禁忌：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 食物：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 神圣空间：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 神圣物品

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事项:

— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在关切教友之间的杀害:

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在关切其他宗教的信徒的谋杀:

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在关切其它政权成员的谋杀:

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在关注性行为:

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在在意撒谎行为:

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在在意誓言的执行:

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然存在在意懒惰：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意巫术：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意非致命的打斗：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意规避风险：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意对长者的不敬：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在乎说长道短的行为：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 超自然存在在意财产犯罪：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在乎对仪礼的正确奉守：
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在乎仪式的演绎：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 超自然存在在意度化无宗教信仰者：
— 是

Notes: It was warned that the sacred knowledge could only be transmitted to people who are "worthy" (morally good, faithful, etc.).

↳ 超自然存在在意经济上的公平：

— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意个人卫生：

— 我不知道

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事物：

— 我不知道

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

— 是

Notes: Individual violation of some common norms and ethics would cause shorten of the lifespan, illness, and misfortune to himself or his family members. When collective violation of certain norms and thus cause a decayed social surrounding, the punishment from the Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement would be the consequence for the corruption of mankind. The forms of the punishment are not limited to mass murder conducted by heavenly soldiers, polluted environment caused by evil beings, and all kinds of natural catastrophes, and endless of wars. Rather than a punishment, it more often described as a purification for a better society.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 只由至上之神完成

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

— 是

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

— 是

↳ 为了强制实施团体准则：

— 是

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

— 是

↳ 随机：

— 否

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 我不知道

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：

— 是

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然惩罚：

— 是

↳ 来世的惩罚包括轻微的感官不悦：

— 是

↳ 来世的惩罚包括极度的感官的不悦：

— 是

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世成为低等生命形式：
— 否

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世到低级领域：
— 否

↳ 其它【请注明】
— 我不知道

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：
— 是

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然惩罚：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括噩运：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括政治上的失败：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括在战斗中失败：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括农作物欠收或恶劣天气：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括出游上灾祸：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括轻微的感觉的不悦：
— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括强烈的感觉的不悦：
— 是

- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括疾病：
 - 是
- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括生育上出问题：
 - 是
- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括后代承受噩运：
 - 是
- ↳ 其它【请注明】
 - 我不知道

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

— 是

Notes: Following basic social values, paying visit and worshipping the deities from time to time, accumulating good deeds by helping other beings, are useful to keep a good record in the administration in charge of life and death. A good record will repay the person with a better afterlife, which means that there will be less or no experience of suffering in the purgatory under earth, be born in a good family in the next life, and a very good chance to be promoted to the sacred realm as a transcendent. The reward from supernatural beings are not narrowed to the afterlife, but also reachable in this life. Have a healthy physical condition, encounter lucky events, and success in career are signals of a devoted person who are favored by supernatural assistance.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 超自然奖赏的来源/目的是已知的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 只由至高的神完成：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 由客观的因果定律完成：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 为了推行团体规范：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 随机：

一否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 在来世赐予超自然奖赏：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然奖赏：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来世的奖赏包括轻微的感官愉悦：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来世的奖赏包括极度的感官愉悦：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来世的奖赏包括永恒的幸福：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来世的奖赏包括转世为更高级生命形式：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 来世的奖赏包括投生到更高级的领域中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 我不知道

↳ 在今世赐予超自然奖赏：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然奖赏：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好运：

— 是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括政治上的成功或权力：

— 是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括在战斗的胜利：

— 我不知道

↳ 今世的奖赏包括和平或社会稳定：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好的收成或风调雨顺：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 今世的奖赏包括出行上一路顺风：

— 我不知道

↳ 今世的奖赏包括轻微感官愉悦：

— 我不知道

↳ 今世的奖赏包括极度的感官愉悦：

— 我不知道

↳ 今世的奖赏包括更好的健康：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 今世的奖赏包括多子多孙：

— 我不知道

↳ 今世的奖赏包括子孙多福

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 我不知道

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

存在某种末世论吗：

— 我不知道

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

— 是

Notes: In the opening chapter of Jin Yunzhong's *Shangqing Lingbao dafa*, the Chapter of Precepts and Principles of the Nature of the Rites (Benfa jielü pin 本法戒律品), he presented Ten Precepts (shijie 十戒). In the Ten Precepts, many are overlapped with Confucians ideas and traditional Chinese view of ethics. It is believed that one can only have great achievement in the pursuing of the Dao by first become a virtuous man in the mundane world. The Ten Precepts are roughly translated below for reference: 1) keep an equal mind, and be honest with yourself; 2) be loyal to your lord and your master, be filial piety to the heaven and earth, and your parents as well; 3) be passionate and benevolent to all beings, be provident and stay out of property; 4) keep secluded and modest, do not gang together; 5) respect and follow the teaching of the Upper Rites (Shangfa 上法, refers to the Dao), be devoted and cultivate yourself; 6) worship the divinities and spirits, never disdain or insult them; 7) have no desire to the food and cloth, because they are nothing but the ancestral pneuma of the Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi zuqi 元始祖氣); 8) use gray water for cleaning, detach from exterior decorations; 9) use your mouth to recite and your heart to pray without putting physical body in hard work; 10) in the seventh day of concentration (dading 大定), you will be in a trance and see the bright light of divinity, and the sacred realm of the Jade Purity.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

— 否

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

— 是

↳ 诚实/忠信/正直：

— 是

↳ 勇敢（在战斗中）：

— 我不知道

↳ 勇敢（一般意义上）：

— 我不知道

↳ 同情心/善解人意/善良/仁爱：

— 是

↳ 仁慈/宽宥/包容：

— 是

↳ 慷慨/博施济众：

— 是

↳ 无私/无私奉献：

— 我不知道

↳ 仗义/正气：

— 是

↳ 仪式纯洁/奉守礼制/戒绝不纯洁之源：

— 是

↳ 对人尊敬/讲礼貌：

— 是

↳ 家庭内的恭顺/孝顺：
— 是

↳ 忠实/忠诚：
— 是

↳ 合作：
— 是

↳ 独立/创造性/自由：
— 我不知道

↳ 节制/节俭：
— 是

↳ 忍耐力/刚毅/耐心：
— 是

↳ 勤奋/自律/卓越：
— 是

↳ 果敢/果断/自信/主动：
— 我不知道

↳ 强壮（身体的）：
— 是

↳ 权力/地位/高贵：
— 否

↳ 谦卑/谦虚：
— 是

↳ 满足/恬静/平和：
— 是

↳ 愉悦/激情/开心：
- 否

↳ 乐观/希望：
- 否

↳ 感恩/答谢：
- 是

↳ 尊敬/敬畏/赞叹：
- 是

↳ 信仰/信念/信任/信奉：
- 是

↳ 智慧/理解力：
- 是

↳ 洞察力/聪颖：
- 是

↳ 美丽/魅力：
- 否

↳ (身体的) 干净/整齐：
- 是

↳ 宗教团体宣扬其他的重要美德：
- 我不知道

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：
- 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 一夫一妻制 (男性)：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 一夫一妻制 (女性)：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (男性)：

— 我不知道

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (女性)：

— 我不知道

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

— 是

Notes: At least three days before a retreat ritual, Daoists who will participate in the ritual have to undergo the phase of fasting. In other time, Daoists are not strictly regulated by a certain eating habit.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物 (对想吃的食物的禁忌) 吗：

— 我不知道

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

— 我不知道

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

— 是

Notes: Except daily practices, several occasions quire Daoists' attendance. For example, the Days of the Three Primes (sanyuan ri 三元日) are the fifteenth day of the first, seventh, and tenth month of a year,

at these three days, some ritual will perform and local communities usually host festivals around religious space.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式 (私人的, 家庭的) 吗：

— 是

Notes: Daoists can perform ritual in their own house, where temporarily transformed into a sacred place. This type of ritual normally under request of some patrons for a specific goal. The participants, if the ritual master him/herself is not enough, the disciples will offer help.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

表演间的平均时间间隔是多少 (以小时计)：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如, 涉及两个或以上的家庭; 包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

— 是

Notes: In the Lingbao dafa, most frequently performed ritual is the Yellow Register Ritual (Huanglu zhai 黄籙齋). It lasts from one day (not very common) to seven days or even more, depending on the costs that the patrons are able to afford. In the Lingbao dafa, it states that if it is the performance of a large-scale Yellow Register Retreat for saving souls, then more than one souls should be released at once. The meaning is that, spending so much money, property, labor, and objects is a very extravagant behavior for the family of the deceased, hence, if the family insists on conducting a large-scale ritual, they have to admit poor people to join and save their dead relatives at the same time. Thus it can be seen, the ritual space would be full of the family members.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 平均来说, 大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点:

— 参与者数量: 11

Notes: The ritual specialists for a standard Huanglu zhai 黄籙齋 (Yellow Register Retreat) which adopts the techniques from the Lingbao dafa are (one on each position): Gaogong fashi高功法師 [Ritual Master of High Merit] Dujiang fashi都講法師 [Ritual Master of Chief Cantor] Fu dujiang fashi副都講法師 [Secondary Ritual Master of Chief Cantor] Jianzhai fashi監齋法師 [Ritual Master of Inspector of the Retreat] Fu jiangzhai fashi副監齋法師 [Secondary Ritual Master of Inspector of the Retreat] Shijing fashi侍經法師 [Ritual Master of Keeper of the Scriptures] Fu shijing fashi副侍經法師 [Secondary Ritual Master of Keeper of the Scriptures] Shixiang fashi侍香法師 [Ritual Master of Keeper of the Incense] Fu shixiang fashi副侍香法師 [Secondary Ritual Master of Keeper of the Incense] Shideng fashi侍燈法師 [Ritual Master of Keeper of the Lamps] Fu shideng fashi副侍燈法師 [Secondary Ritual Master of Keeper of the Lamps]

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少 (以小时计):

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 平均间隔【小时】: 72

Notes: Three days on average.

— 平均间隔【小时】: 36

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 是否存在正统性审查:

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如, 通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督, 诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

— 一个帝国

Notes: From the Northern Song dynasty (960-1127 CE) to the Ming dynasty (1368-1644 CE), during which the Lingbao dafa was formed and most popularized in the Jiangnan region, the Chinese society and political system were centralized by authority.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

— 我不知道

Notes: It depends on the scale and financial capacity of each monastery. The religious groups in tradition China are the main participants of charity which includes relieving poverty, providing food, adopting infants, and sheltering homeless people. However, there has no strict rules to regulate and systemize this function of charity. Therefore, it seems like that all the help is provided voluntarily that share no pattern.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

— 否

Notes: It is a feature of the Tiantai Lingbao that the teaching of the Lingbao dafa, as the masters believed, should not be holding back to ordained Daoists only. Thanks to this idea, the spreading of Lingbao tradition quickly full the area of Jiangnan around the Southern Song time. Many elites and common people who have previous believes in Confucianism, Buddhism or any popular religions, are welcomed to convert to the belief of the Lingbao dafa without abandoning other faiths.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

— 是

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Since the Northern Wei dynasty (386-534), the government set up departments specializing in dealing with Daoist affairs. Although the title of the officials, name of the department, and the constitutions are not exactly the same, the angle of regulating the religious Daoist groups is the same all along its development to nowadays.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体提供基础交通设施吗：

— 是

Notes: It is propagated that for both religious practitioners and common people, to build road and bridge for the public is a great way to increase merit. As long as the economy permits, the religious specialists, sometimes cooperated with local elites (xiangshen 鄉紳), are in charge of transportation infrastructures in the village.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

基础交通设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗:

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗:

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗:

— 未知领域

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗:

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗:

— 未知领域

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗:

— 是

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗:

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗:

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗:

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

— 是

Notes: Except traditional Chinese writing, we can also see the writing, or some may call painting in talisman (fu 符) that commonly used during ritual performance. Besides, in the Lingbao dafa, there is a distinct writing system called Celestial Writing (tianwen 天文). It is not only a type of seal character (zhuan 篆), but a very sacred and profound one which equal with the origin of the world, the Dao. See an entire book on this topic: Hsieh Shu-wei 謝世維, Tianjie zhiwen: Weijin Nanbei chao Lingbao jingdian yanjiu 天界之文：魏晉南北朝靈寶經典研究 (Celestial Writing: A Study of Lingbao Scriptures in Wei, Jin, The Northern and Southern Dynasties). Taipei: Taiwan shangwu, 2010.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

这种独特的书面语的使用仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

— 是

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 是

Notes: Traditional Chinese writing, regulated by Chinese empire as official written language, is the normal one in the Daoist Canon.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 是

Notes: Traditional Chinese

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 宗教专家 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

— 是

Notes: The Lingbao Daoism uses the same Chinese Lunar Calendar as the rest of society formulated by the empire.

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

— 是

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】：

— 小规模农业/园艺花园或果园

— 其他【请在评论中说明】

Notes: The monastery accepts offerings from official supports like the court and local communities, also from patrons no matter who is rich or poor. Religious specialists living a monastic life usually farm for a living in their field. For those who live in seclusion in remote mountains, food will either be gathered by their own or they have patrons regularly provide food and bring to them.

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

— 是

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】

— 收集

— 小规模农业/园艺花园或果园

— 其他【请在评论中说明】

Notes: The monastery accepts offerings from official supports like the court and local communities, also from patrons no matter who is rich or poor. Religious specialists living a monastic life usually farm for a living in their field. For those who live in seclusion in remote mountains, food will either be gathered by their own or they have patrons regularly provide food and bring to them.

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